

FEATURES OF THE USE OF STYLISTIC DEVICES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK BASED ON PRIDE AND PREJUDICE BY JAMES AUSTIN.

Lobar Ibragimova Daniyorovna

Surkhandarya Region Termiz State University,

1 st master of linguistics (English)

Panjiyeva Nasiba

Ph.D .Assistant Professor of Tersu

Abstract: Based on James Austin's Pride and Prejudice, this article provides information about the features of the use of stylistic tools in English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: Linguistics, stylistic tools, English language, Uzbek language, lexical antithesis.

Аннотация: На основе романа Джеймса Остина «Гордость и предубеждение» в данной статье представлена информация об особенностях использования стилистических средств в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: Языкознание, стилистические средства, английский язык, узбекский язык, лексическая антитеза.

Introduction:

There are different branches of linguistics. Among them, stylistics is distinguished by color. Stylistics (Greek: stylos - writing, letter stick), stylistics, methodology - researches the language styles of linguistics, explores the essence and peculiarities of the functional folding of the language from the point of view of synchrony and diachrony at the lexic-phraseological, phonetic, morphological, word formation and syntactic levels. network that describes the norms and methods of using literary language in various linguistic situations, in various types and genres of written literature, in various spheres of social life. Stylistics studies semantic and expressive

subtleties in parallel synonymous language expressions, interrelated variants of linguistic units. In such options, there will be an opportunity to choose the one that is necessary for a particular speech situation. The stylistic construction of the language allows it to perform specific speech tasks through certain functional styles, in which speakers direct the participants of the dialogue to certain opinions, effective and effective speech communication between them, resulting in more than communication. the intended goals and objectives are achieved and mutual understanding is achieved. [4]Among them, antithesis enhances the meaning through antonyms, and artistic devices help to make proverbs more effective. It condenses them, takes the lead in expressing a clear judgment. Antithesis is one of the stylistic methods, which is built on the basis of opposite meanings and ensures that reality is bright and symbolic. There are two types of antithesis in English, they are logical antithesis and lexical antonyms. Lexical antithesis is based on the lexical meaning of the antonym words: "Many are called but few are chosen." Logical antithesis is based directly on the nature of the context is created. It uses words and phrases that do not contradict each other and creates a contrast between the reality in the text: We are young, friend, like the flowers, You are old, friend, like the tree, What concern have you with ours? You are dying, we 're to be It is very true, I'm dying, You are roses still in bud...(J. Mansfield) Antithesis is one of the arts widely used in English literature, especially poetry is one. The main character of the novel "Pride and Prejudice" is Elizabeth, the second daughter of the Bennet family. He is intelligent, intelligent, careful and observes the nature of people. The events of the work, the character of the characters are told from his point of view. Readers of the novel will have new information only when he has it. He reads a lot of books, the conclusions he gets from them encourage him to use common sense.[5]Because of this, he has high self-confidence and can behave freely everywhere. His tongue and tongue are one, and he utters only what he thinks. He is far from flattery and false politeness. He criticizes such attitudes in society through laughter. But at the same time, he is not completely cut off from his society. Like other

girls, she wants a happy marriage. He believes that a happy marriage should be built on the basis of mutual trust, respect and love. However, his sharp tongue, tendency to make hasty decisions, stubbornness cause him to go astray. We can clearly see this in his relationship with Mr. Darcy and Wickham. At the beginning of the play, he concludes that Darcy is arrogant and lacking in positive human qualities, because of his pride, he does not see the good qualities in him and doesn't allow readers to see it either. Because he wants to like Wickham, he encourages the reader to like him too. By the end of the novel, Elizabeth realizes that people can be multidimensional and that it is important to use new information to reevaluate first impressions. [3]Due to this change in her character, she is happily married to a man who truly loves and respects her, as she wishes. She is a free and healthy thinking girl. For this reason, his father loves him and shares his opinions with him. He believes that couples love, understand and respect each other is an important factor in building a family. He stands firmly in his views and achieves happiness thanks to his determination. The author proves his determined actions with arguments from his relations with the characters of the work. [2]The relationships between Elizabeth and Mrs. Bennet, Elizabeth and Mr. Collins, Elizabeth and Caroline Bingley, Elizabeth and Darcy, and Elizabeth and Lady Catherine are clear examples of this. In the passage below, we can see Mrs. Bennet's attitude towards Elizabeth, who is suffering from his stubbornness, after her daughter rejects Mr. Collins' proposal. "Aye, there she comes," continued Mrs. Bennet, "looking as unconceived as -may be, and caring no more for us than if we were at York, provided she can have her own way. But I tell you, Miss Lizzy - if you take it into your head to go on refusing every offer of marriage in this way, you will never get a husband at all - and I am sure I do not know who is to maintain you when your father is dead. I shall not be able to keep you - and so I wam you I have done with you from this every day. I told you in the library, you know, that I should never speak to you again, and you will find me as good as my word. [1]I have no pleasure in talking to undutiful children .

Discussion and result:

Mr. Collins has a position in society, a steady income, and after Mr. Bennet's death, an estate in Longbourn. He believes that any girl will accept his marriage proposal. When he first arrives in Longbourn, the Bennets plans to propose to Jane, the most beautiful eldest daughter in her family, but with talk of Jane's imminent engagement After r, he changes his mind and asks for the hand of Elizabeth, who is not very beautiful, but intelligent. For Mr. Collins, it doesn't matter who the spouse is. He wants to marry for his own interests, that is, in order not to spend too much money on household chores, and also according to Lady Catherine's advice. For this reason, the rejection he received from Elizabeth had no effect on him. The next day, he proposed to Charlotte, Elizabeth's close friend. Because he is such an insensitive person. Naturally, Elizabeth is a smart girl. She definitely does not want to marry such a person. But Mrs. Bennet, whose only goal in life is to get her daughters married, is angry. He is angry that he could not control his daughter, that he could not bend her to his will, and his nerves are straining. He is trying to explain that what he did is bad for his future and nobody will take care of him after his father's death. All the actions of the mother for her daughter were nullified. "I do assure you, sir, that I have no pretensions whatsoever to that kind of elegance which consists in tormenting a respectable man. I would rather be paid the compliment of being beloved sincere. I thank you again and again for the honour you have done me in your proposals, but to accept theme is absolutely impossible. My feelings in every respect forbid it. Can I speak plainer? Do not consider me now as an elegant female, intending to plauge you, but as a rational creature, speaking the truth from her heart.

While Mr. Collins had chalked up her answer to girlish masculinity, Elizabeth had resolutely refused him as an intelligent mature woman. Collins' proposal did not meet Elizabeth's criteria for a happy marriage. She wanted to marry a man who truly loved her and respected her, not for a comfortable life like some girls of her time. While her mother tried to dissuade Elizabeth from her views, her father supported her.

Antithesis is also a stylistic device often used in English proverbs. Opposite meanings are created through adjectives, adverbs, or noun phrases. Promise little, but do much (proverb) In this proverb, the words little and much form an antithesis. The content is fully revealed with the help of antonyms. It is the same as its equivalent in Uzbek. "Say less, do more" in terms of meaning, when we compare the two proverbs, both of them are antonyms using idioms. Better an open enemy than a false friend (proverb). In the above proverb, enemy and friend are opposing. Expresses the full meaning through the words enemy and friend. Like Uzbek folk proverbs, English folk proverbs are one of the most widespread genres of English folklore. They often show common aspects similar to Uzbek proverbs in terms of their structure, study in folklore, and other aspects. Because most of the proverbs used in our speech today are created in the past and clearly express the limitations and contradictions of the people's psychology and worldview. Therefore, it is necessary to collect folk proverbs and study their layers characteristic of different periods in nature from the point of view of consistent classification. For example, one of the Uzbek folk proverbs "The rich feed the rich, the water flows into the stream" is difficult to understand at a glance, in which period of society and by which class of representatives. If the proverb is used in the speech of the working people, it serves the interests of this class or vice versa.

Among the proverbs that belong to the Uzbek and English folk proverbs:

English: A bad beginning makes a bad ending

Uzbek: When there is evil, ice falls on snow.

English: A good beginning makes a good ending.

The fact that the outcome of a work depends on how it begins is also reflected in proverbs. Usually, the end of the work we start depends on how we start it and the attitude of those around us. That is why it is expressed in proverbs that if we start well, it is good, and on the contrary, if we start badly, we will end badly. The proverb is a conclusion, but it is not yet the final destination, the beginning of imagination. A proverb is a conclusion in a certain case, and a hypothesis in another case, and it crosses

new problems. The value of the proverb is known when its meaning, which requires deep penetration, is explained. Interpreting proverbs in discussions, conversations, and debates is widespread among the people. If the people praise hardworking people with their wise words, they praise the lazy and the lazy ones who avoid work. The word of the people is sharp and affects like a weapon. Indeed, in the world, great philosophers and poets grow out of ordinary people from the working people. Both of them enjoy the source of wisdom created by the people. In folk proverbs, friendship and brotherhood, work and courage, joy and happiness, sadness and pain, defeat and victory, love and emigration are feelings. they find their expression. In Uzbek proverbs, we can find many proverbs with antithesis, that is, the art of contrast:

If you walk with good deeds, you will reach your heart's content.

if you walk with evil, you will be ashamed;

He eats good food and bad food;

Be a king in your country until you become a king in another country;

United - different,

Not united - bad.

In the proverbs mentioned above, the meaning is clearly explained in a short way with the help of antonyms. From these examples, it can be seen that proverbs focus on the educational aspect of comparison. Proverbs expressed by relative opposition are structurally 2-component proverbs, which is one of the important features of antithesis. The first part of the compound sentence is expressed in such a way that it is clearly felt that the second sentence is needed after it.

In conclusion, Antithesis is one of the stylistic devices, mainly compound sentences used in proverbs and poetry. English and Uzbek folk proverbs differ from other genres of folklore by their own characteristics. That is, in them, the opinion is expressed in the form of a clear, complete conclusion, a clear judgment, the expression of a certain judgment in a logical consistency, sharp polarity is leading, and it is possible to use it in its own and figurative meanings. In addition, proverbs show their

universal aspects by predominating aspects such as exemplification and advice. The use of stylistic tools in proverbs increases its range of influence and stylistic color. In proverbs, especially metaphors, similes, adjectives, comparisons are often used. Tazad tool is also actively involved. As a result, the balance in the use of formal and substantive arts is evident in folk proverbs.

Reference:

1. Galperin I. R. Stylistics of the English language. Moskva. Knijnyy dom "LIBROKOM", Izd. 5, 2013.[1]
2. Tikhonova E. V. Mediatext as an instrument of verbal diagnosis of confessional tension // Mirovye cultural-linguistic and political space: innovation and communication: collection of scientific works. M.: TransArt, 2014. S.[2]
3. Shomaksudov A. and others, stylistics of the Uzbek language. - T.: Teacher, 1983, [3]
4. M. Khalilova: "Basics of Uzbek language stylistics", "Fergana" publishing house, 2009. [4]
5. www.ziyonet.uz[5]